

Recurrence of iron-deficiency anemia in Peruvian Andean children aged 12 to 35 months living in poverty: the role of ferrous sulfate supplementation and associated factors

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Abstract

Introduction: There are few studies on the factors that cause iron-deficiency anemia (IDA) recurrence in Andean children living in income poverty.

Objective: This study aimed to identify risk factors related to health determinants for anemia recurrence in Peruvian Andean children aged 12 to 35 months.

Methodology: The mothers of 189 children (63 cases of recurrence of anemia) in the Sánchez Carrión Province in the northern highlands of Peru were evaluated with a 40-question survey of health determinants (Cronbach's alpha = 0.70).

Results: The cases (recurrence) and controls (no recurrence) were comparable according to sex, age, residence altitude, and poverty level. Of 18 factors analyzed by bivariate analysis and binary logistic regression, six risk factors for recurrence were identified: malnutrition OR = 4.89, 95% CI 1.727–13.828; negligent care OR = 3.33, 95% CI 1.229–9.004; poor hygiene habits OR = 5.50, 95% CI 2.165–13.972; overcrowding OR = 3.16, 95% CI 1.125–8.869; inaccessibility of ferrous sulfate OR = 7.18, 95% CI 2.253–22.903; and child rejection of ferrous sulfate OR = 14.65, 95% CI 5.056–42.419.

Conclusions: This study identified complex physiological and socioeconomic determinants associated with IDA relapse. Effective IDA reduction strategies require context-specific comprehensive approaches that integrate culturally relevant education, improve living conditions, provide access to palatable iron-rich foods, and increase iron supplementation availability and adherence.

Keywords

iron-deficiency anemia, ferrous sulfate, risk factor, preschool children, poverty

Introduction

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most common hematological condition worldwide, affecting approximately 2 billion people. Anemia is defined as the condition of having blood hemoglobin concentrations below established limits. These limits vary with gender, age, and residence altitude. For children between 6 and 59 months of age, a blood hemoglobin level below 7 g/dL is considered severe anemia, with mild and moderate anemia defined as 10–11 g/dL and 7–10 g/dL, respectively (World Health Organization 2010; GBD 2021 Anaemia Collaborators 2023; Ministerio de Salud Perú 2024).

The main cause of IDA is an iron-deficient diet, which is insufficient to produce blood hemoglobin and, consequently, red blood cells. This inhibits oxygen transport in the body, especially to the brain. Without oxygen, brain development can be permanently impaired. This can cause lifelong disability, especially if IDA occurs in the first two years of life, when brain growth and development are most important. IDA can inhibit cognitive and motor development and cause weakness, dizziness, drowsiness, irritability, and attention deficit, all of which have serious impacts that last through adulthood (Allali et al. 2017; Lozoff et al. 2022; World Health Organization 2025).

There are population-level strategies to address the problem of IDA by increasing iron intake: the most widely used is ferrous sulfate supplementation (Colegio Médico del Perú 2023). This compound is a soluble iron salt that is absorbed by the body, where it is used to produce hemoglobin and red blood cells. Therefore, it is expected that this treatment would result in prompt recovery and protection against IDA recurrence (National Institutes of Health 2025). However, ferrous sulfate supplementation programs in children aged 12 to 59 months have had mixed results, so this intervention cannot be considered a cure in itself but as part of a comprehensive treatment program (Colegio Médico del Perú 2023). Negative factors involved in ferrous sulfate supplementation include low adherence, gastrointestinal side effects, and poor intestinal absorption of non-heme iron, especially when inflammatory processes or diets high in inhibitors such as phytates and polyphenols, coexist (Kumar et al. 2020; Kumar et al. 2021).

Therefore, many recommendations emphasize that simple supplementation with ferrous sulfate is not sufficient to reduce the presence or recurrence of IDA: the implementation of multiple effective prevention techniques is required. Therefore, the Pan American Health Organization recommends the need to strengthen technical skills and comprehensive interventions during child development to prevent IDA and IDA recurrence. Such a program should include measures to prevent premature birth or low birth weight, promote exclusive breastfeeding through at least the first six months of life, provide an iron-rich diet, and provide iron supplementation if necessary (Freire 1997; Comité Nacional de Hematología, Oncología y Medicina Transfusional 2017; World Health Organization 2025).

Worldwide, IDA rates vary greatly by geography and age. The highest prevalence of IDA occurs in children under five years of age who live in developing countries (Kumar et al. 2021; Gallagher 2022). For decades, childhood IDA has been a common, yet implacable, problem in the Andes mountains of Ecuador, Peru, and Bolivia, with approximately half of all children affected (Garrido-Salazar et al. 2019). Children living in poverty in these regions have higher IDA rates than those who are not poor.

In Peru, IDA remains a serious problem, particularly among preschool children and women of childbearing age. Recent data indicate that approximately 40% of Peruvian children aged between 6 and 35 months have anemia, with iron deficiency the most common cause (Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática 2020; Alvarado et al. 2022). To confront this problem, the Peruvian government proposed national strategies to reduce and control maternal and child IDA (Ministerio de Salud Perú 2017); however, success remains limited. Further compounding the problem is that some children suffer relapses of IDA despite these strategies, requiring a longer-term focus. Although anemia treatment and prevention have received significant attention among researchers, understanding anemia relapse is a less studied area.

Therefore, to address IDA in Peru, it is reasonable to ask why some children, despite receiving ferrous sulfate, have a recurrence of IDA. It is likely that IDA recurrence is associated with the accumulation of individual, social, environmental, and economic factors rather than a single determinant of health, also known as a health field (Lalonde 1981; McKee et al. 2017). These determinants are factors that influence people's health that cover four major categories: lifestyles and personal behaviors, human biology (age, disease, genetics), physical and social environmental quality, and health service quality and accessibility (Lalonde 1981; Dávalos Rodríguez 2017).

Given the difficulty in solving the problem of IDA in Andean Peru and that supplementation-only interventions often result in recurrence of IDA, our objective was to compare the determinants of health between children who suffered IDA recurrence and those who did not. This information would provide suggestions for a more effective IDA reduction program. We chose Sánchez Carrión Province, Peru, for the study location because it is the largest province in the La Libertad region and serves as a pilot for healthcare interventions.

Materials and methods

Design and sampling

This is an observational, analytical, case-control study of children aged 12 to 35 months who had anemia, defined by blood hemoglobin below 11.0 g/dL. All study participants were first diagnosed with IDA and treated with ferrous sulfate (3 mg/kg/day) for 6 months. The participants were then monitored for up to 18 months after ferrous sulfate supplementation.

A decrease in hemoglobin to below 11.0 g/dL during the monitoring period was classified as a relapse. Cases were defined as children who had a relapse of IDA after treatment, while controls were children who recovered from IDA without relapse. The case-to-control ratio was 1:2.

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Commission of the School of Medicine of the National University of Trujillo, Peru, with approval code 312-2022-UNT-FM-C.E., dated 22 October 2022. Mothers provided their voluntary written consent, and the resulting data were anonymized. Participants received no incentive to participate or not participate in the study.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Children aged 12 to 35 months, diagnosed with anemia in 2021, and resident in Sánchez Carrión Province were

included in the study. Economic poverty was determined by professionals at the Sánchez Carrión health center using questionnaires and interviews based on guidelines from the Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática (Peru). Children with a history of comorbidities such as cancer, chronic kidney failure, or vector-borne diseases were excluded, along with children whose mothers refused to participate.

Sample size determination

In 2022, there were 1566 IDA diagnoses in the province of Sánchez Carrión, of which 148 were cases of recurrence. This information was personally provided to the authors by the Red de Salud Sánchez Carrión. Using EpiData V.4.2.0 and assuming an odds ratio of 4.910 (Llaca Merma 2022), $R=2$, and a confidence level of 95%, 63 cases and 126 controls were required to achieve the desired statistical power. Study participants were selected by simple random sampling (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Key elements of study design.

Survey instrument

A 40-question survey (supplementary data 1) was developed and validated for mothers of the child participants to assess IDA recurrence, ferrous sulfate supplementation, and determinants of health among cases and controls. The questionnaire requested the dates of occurrence and recurrence (if applicable) of IDA and continued to ask about lifestyle (diet, violence/safety, and hygiene habits; 4 questions), environment (quality of water and housing, crowding, waste disposal, and religious prohibitions; 10 questions), health services (quality of care, availability of ferrous sulfate, access to care, acceptance of ferrous sulfate by children, adherence to the treatment plan, including growth and development monitoring, and immunization adherence; 16 questions), and human biology (maternal anemia, birth weight, prematurity, breastfeeding, and disease prevalence; 9 questions).

The questionnaire was validated by expert judgment (3 nurses and an epidemiologist), and its reliability was determined in a pilot test of 5 cases and controls, which produced a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.7, which is generally considered good.

Procedure

The Sánchez Carrión Health Network provided the authors with the names and addresses of preschool IDA patients. The authors visited the homes of each selected participant between October 2022 and July 2023, where they requested that the mothers of the cases provide written informed consent and complete a questionnaire that took approximately 40 minutes. When available, the authors also reviewed the growth and development control card provided by health services. Responses to the survey and data from the control card were recorded for each case and control.

Data processing

Bivariate (case-control method) and multivariate analysis (binary logistic regression, conditional progressive forward method) using EPIINFO 7 and IBM SPSS v. 26 to identify risk factors among health determinants. The latter program was also used for PROXSCAL multidimensional scaling to associate categories of factors through their Euclidean distances in a biplot (Hair et al. 2010).

Results

A total of 189 surveys were completed, with a 2:1 ratio of controls to cases (Table 1). The case and control groups did not differ significantly in terms of sex, age, domicile poverty level, altitude of residence, or anemia severity. Therefore, both groups were demographically comparable, indicating proper randomization of cases and controls.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of cases and controls.

	Cases		Controls		χ^2	P
	number	%	number	%		
TOTAL	63	100.0	126	100.0		
Gender						
Male	31	49.2	55	43.7	0.523	0.469
Female	32	50.8	71	56.3		
Age						
1 year old	28	44.4	57	45.2	0.011	0.917
2 years old	35	55.6	69	54.8		
% of domicile location in extreme poverty						
<40%	19	30.2	44	34.9	0.467	0.791
40% to 60%	9	14.3	16	12.7		
more 60%	35	55.6	64	50.8		
Altitude of residence, m						
< 3000	22	34.9	29	23.0	3.315	0.191
3000 to 3499	34	54.0	84	66.7		
> 3500	7	11.1	13	10.3		
Anemia level						
Mild	44	69.8	87	69.0	0.012	0.911
Moderate*	19	30.2	35	27.8		
Severe*	0	0.0	4	3.2		

* Combined for statistical analysis.

The results of the health questionnaire allowed comparison of health determinants between cases and controls (Table 2). Of the 18 determinants tested, 15 were significantly different between cases and controls ($p < 0.05$). Prematurity, nonexclusive breastfeeding, and follow-up for growth and development were excluded due to technical reasons. A limitation of the bivariate model is that it assumes independence of effects.

Therefore, a binary logistic regression multivariate analysis was conducted on the same data, in which all factors were assessed simultaneously, allowing holistic identification of the determinants of IDA relapse in children (Table 3).

Table 3 reports the findings of the binary logistic regression, in which six risk factors were identified that together most strongly explain the recurrence of IDA in the study population. The factors with the highest odds ratios for IDA relapse are associated with ferrous sulfate supplementation.

Fig. 2 displays case-control data on childhood anemia recurrence for 18 health determinants (Lalonde 1981), analyzed using a multidimensional scaling model to assess interdependence and organize factors based on their affinities, measured by Euclidean distances. The biplot reveals a close grouping of points for 17 of the health determinants.

The normalized stress level and dispersion index for the goodness-of-fit model were 0.020 and 0.98, respectively—both considered acceptable. Finally, Tucker's congruence coefficient was 0.998. These results indicate that there is a large interdependence between determinants of health and IDA recurrence.

Among the 15 factors closest to A2 (childhood anemia recurrence), the six factors identified in the binary regression were also found to be significant (in red).

Table 2. Bivariate analysis of cases and controls of factors associated with determinants of health.

Determinants of Health	Abbreviation	Cases		Controls		χ^2	P	OR	LL CI 95%	UL CI 95%
		number	%	number	%					
Child rejection of ferrous sulfate	RFS	44	69.8	29	23.0	38.847	0.000	7.75	3.92	15.28
Poor hygiene habits	BHH	40	63.5	25	19.8	35.467	0.000	7.03	3.58	13.77
Low birth weight	LBW	17	27.0	10	7.9	12.444	0.000	4.29	1.83	10.06
Negligent care	NC	36	57.1	31	24.6	19.434	0.000	4.08	2.15	7.77
Non-compliance with growth and development follow-up	NGD	9	14.3	5	4.0	6.519	0.011	4.03	1.29	12.6
Malnutrition	MNT	33	52.4	30	23.8	15.429	0.000	3.52	1.85	6.69
Ferrous sulfate inaccessible	FSS	25	39.7	18	14.3	15.414	0.000	3.95	1.94	8.03
Precarious housing	PH	33	52.4	29	23.0	16.430	0.000	3.68	1.93	7.02
Overcrowding	OC	46	73.0	56	44.4	13.801	0.000	3.38	1.75	6.53
Maternal anemia	MA	48	76.2	63	50.0	11.886	0.000	3.20	1.63	6.30
Poor drinking water quality	PQW	31	49.2	31	24.6	11.534	0.000	2.97	1.57	5.63
Difficult Access to health services	DHS	18	28.6	15	11.9	8.095	0.004	2.96	1.37	6.38
Poor healthcare quality	PTH	32	50.8	34	27.0	10.477	0.001	2.79	1.49	5.25
Prevalent diseases	PD	40	63.5	52	41.3	8.302	0.004	2.48	1.33	4.62
Religious prejudices	RP	19	30.2	19	15.1	5.945	0.015	2.43	1.18	5.03
Non-compliance with exclusive breastfeeding	NEB	44	69.8	91	72.2	0.117	0.733	0.89	0.46	1.73
Lack of improved sewer services	LD	63	100.0	102	81.0	13.745	0.000	Indef		
Prematurity ^a	PRE	8	12.7	2	1.6	8.249	0.004	9.02	1.85	43.86

^alow frequency.

Table 3. Binary logistic regression analysis of IDA relapse factors between cases and controls.

Determinants of Health	Abbreviation	Wald Test	P	Exp(B) (OR)	LI CI 95%	UI CI 95%
Malnutrition	MNT	8.941	0.003	4.887	1.727	13.828
Negligent Care	NC	5.596	0.018	3.326	1.229	9.004
Poor hygiene habits	BHH	12.843	0.000	5.500	2.165	13.972
Overcrowding	OC	4.769	0.029	3.159	1.125	8.869
Ferrous sulfate inaccessible	FSS	11.109	0.001	7.183	2.253	22.903
Child rejection of ferrous sulfate	RFS	24.471	0.000	14.646	5.056	42.419

Figure 2. Biplot of risk factors for IDA relapse (point A2) in the population studied. In red are factors identified to have a significant association with the risk of IDA relapse.

Discussion

IDA is a significant global health problem that negatively affects childhood development. It is especially prevalent in low- and middle-income countries such as Peru, where four out of ten children under 36 months of age suffer from it (Zavaleta and Astete-Robilliard 2017; Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática 2020). Although its etiology is known, various science-based health interventions have produced mixed results in reducing IDA prevalence (Tokumura and Mejía 2023). In fact, the high prevalence of IDA persists in Peru despite governmental promotion of nutritional interventions (Fuentes-Parrales 2024). This indicates that IDA treatment requires a multifaceted approach. Understanding the local conditions associated with the appearance of IDA in children can therefore better inform health interventions.

In the present investigation, we used the Lalonde model to associate IDA relapse with determinants of health (Lalonde 1981). Determinants associated with IDA recurrence were identified in Andean children previously treated with ferrous sulfate. Of the 18 determinants initially evaluated using bivariate analysis, 16 showed statistically significant differences between cases and controls. Using the multivariate logistic regression model, six main factors emerged as having a significant influence on IDA recurrence: rejection or nonavailability of ferrous sulfate supplements, malnutrition, neglectful care, poor hygiene habits, and overcrowding (Table 3). All had estimated odds ratios greater than 3.

Child rejection of ferrous sulfate had the highest odds ratio among the identified factors. Ferrous sulfate supplementation has been proven effective in treating IDA (Powers et al. 2017). However, it also produces undesirable side effects such as nausea, diarrhea, constipation, stomach discomfort, and appetite loss. These adverse effects have been shown to be major reasons for poor adherence, tolerance, and rejection of treatment, significantly reducing its clinical effectiveness (Powers et al. 2017; Kumar et al. 2021; Lozoff 2022). Additionally, ferrous sulfate consumption can cause teeth staining, caries, and pulp disease in children treated for anemia (Leon-Rodríguez et al. 2024). To minimize these adverse effects, weekly administration has been proposed instead of daily intake, showing similar efficacy in preventing anemia (Varea 2023).

Another option is the development of new iron formulations with fewer side effects and better palatability. Various formulations and supplementation methods have been evaluated, including liposomal iron, heme iron, and polymaltose iron, which offer better gastrointestinal tolerance and higher adherence compared to traditional formulations (Hussain 2019; Bah 2024). For instance, a recent study by Ebea-Ugwuanyi et al. (2024) found that young children found fortified powdered iron formulations and liquid supplements more palatable than ferrous sulfate. Furthermore, approaches such as nanotechnology-based iron supplements and advanced dietary fortification, as outlined by Trivedi and

Barve (2021), offer promising alternatives for improving treatment efficacy. Food fortification, as successfully implemented in Costa Rica (Martorell et al. 2015), and gut microbiota modulation using prebiotics (Ahmad et al. 2021) represent additional strategies for increasing blood iron concentration. Several of these formulations demonstrate more efficient absorption rates, especially when administered alongside vitamin C-rich foods. Additionally, co-supplementation of folic acid with iron sulfate has been shown to improve iron levels among Brazilian children more than iron sulfate alone (Hadler et al. 2008). These findings reinforce the importance of improving not only the availability of supplements and adjuvants but also their acceptance and adherence.

Problems with iron sulfate access also continue to be a significant barrier to anemia control. In regions with rudimentary health systems, the supply chain for iron sulfate is often disrupted, reducing access to treatment (Hussain 2019). Furthermore, limited economic resources constrain the implementation of sustainable supplementation programs (Lopez de Romaña et al. 2023).

These results align with previous research, such as that of Al-Kassab-Córdova et al. (2023), demonstrating the influence of socioeconomic, public health, and cultural factors on the effectiveness of conventional supplementation strategies. (Kumar et al. 2021; Gallagher 2022). For example, Al-Kassab-Córdova et al. (2023) demonstrated that maternal education and rural or high-altitude residence are critical determinants of childhood IDA inequality in Peru, mirroring the socioeconomic influences observed here. Our findings further demonstrate how socioeconomic, public health, educational, and cultural factors shape the effectiveness of standard supplementation approaches. Structural barriers such as malnutrition and limited access to treatment are causes of IDA and IDA relapse, while difficult socioenvironmental conditions, such as overcrowding and poor hygiene, increase the risk of infections that impair iron absorption. Overcrowding has been consistently linked to higher rates of respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, which deteriorate the nutritional status of children and exacerbate anemia (Villalpando et al. 2021; Lozoff et al. 2022). Overcrowding also limits the implementation of adequate sanitation measures, worsening the situation (Villalpando et al. 2021). Cultural barriers further impact adherence to iron supplementation. For example, traditional beliefs and a lack of trust in health professionals can reduce the acceptance of medical treatments (Bar-Zeev et al. 2013). Additionally, inadequate complementary feeding and limited access to iron-rich foods are significant contributors to anemia prevalence (Tadesse et al. 2022). These factors make proper nutrition and supplementation difficult in resource-poor settings (Black et al. 2013). Therefore, it is essential to develop culturally adapted interventions that involve community leaders and promote education on the benefits of iron in a locally relevant manner (Black et al. 2013).

We not only identified several determinants associated with IDA relapse, but our multidimensional analysis biplot also revealed a high interdependence between them. This suggests that interventions targeting only a single determinant are likely to have limited impact. Comprehensive strategies are needed that include both effective supplementation and improvements in living conditions, nutrition, and hygiene education for affected families. Educational programs should be adapted to local contexts to ensure their success. Such programs should be designed with community collaboration, focused on improving knowledge about anemia and nutrition, and are more likely to succeed than traditional top-down approaches (Black et al. 2013). Implementing such programs may involve training local health promoters, using visual education, and distributing culturally appropriate materials (Tadesse 2022). In this regard, Angeles et al. (2019) showed that integrated nutrition education and school programs significantly improved maternal knowledge and children's nutritional status, potentially reducing IDA recurrence through better household hygiene and nutrition in the Philippines. Similarly, Omer et al. (2023) found that nutrition education combined with iron-rich foods, such as eggs, significantly increased hemoglobin levels and reduced childhood IDA in Ethiopia. Similarly, a study in low-income areas of Ancón, Lima, Peru, found that a pharmaceutical care intervention program—focused on anemia, parasitosis, nutrition, and hygiene practices for caregivers—combined with pharmacological treatment and follow-up, resulted in a statistically significant increase in hemoglobin levels (Alcalá Pimentel et al. 2023).

The limitations of this study include the lack of previous research on childhood IDA recurrence, making direct comparisons difficult. In addition, scattered housing and adverse weather conditions increased data collection time, which could have affected the quality of responses. Finally, the length of the questionnaire may have influenced the quality of the responses, especially for the questions toward the end of the survey (Medina 2023).

Future research should explore innovative strategies to overcome the logistical, socioeconomic, and cultural barriers identified in this study that limit access to and acceptance of iron supplements. Additional work could also include evaluating educational interventions aimed at improving eating and hygiene habits in vulnerable communities. Another promising area of research is the characterization of new supplements and iron-rich foods that have high iron absorption rates and are both palatable and accessible to rural communities.

Conclusion

This study provides evidence on the nature of IDA recurrence among rural Andean children, finding that the causes of IDA are complex and include both physiological and socioeconomic determinants. Therefore,

the sustained reduction of IDA in rural areas requires a comprehensive strategy that considers local conditions and encompasses culturally appropriate education, improved living conditions, access to palatable iron-rich foods, and the availability, acceptance, and adherent use of ferrous sulfate or other supplements.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Health Network Sánchez Carrión - Huamachuco, La Libertad, Peru.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

CNVC and JJHS contributed to the conceptualization of the study. Methodology was developed by JJHS, JENO, and JVCF. CNVC and JENO were responsible for software development. Validation was carried out by JJHS and JVCF. Formal analysis was performed by CNVC and JENO. CNVC and JJHS conducted the investigation. Resources were provided by CNVC, JJHS, JENO, and JVCF. Data curation was managed by JJHS, JENO, and JVCF. CNVC, JJHS, and JVCF contributed to writing the original draft as well as reviewing and editing the manuscript. Visualization was done by CNVC. Supervision was provided by JJHS and JVCF. Project administration was handled by CNVC. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Ethical approval

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Data type: pdf

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Supplementary material 2

Statistical analysis

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